

Employees' Organizational Commitment among the None-Academic Staffs of Public Universities along the Lake Region, Kenya

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Abstract: With the current on-going organizational transformation, the psychological contract between the University employer and the support staff is open to violation. Several University employees consider their psychological contract as effective compared to those considered normative and continuance. The psychological contract is a determinant of organizational commitment among non-academic staffs and in the case of public Universities along the lake region, there is an organizational commitment failure attributed to staff attitude and psychological rewards, thus causing a psychological contract breach. This paper discussed the employees' organizational commitment among the none-academic staffs of public universities along the Lake Region in Kenya. The study was premised on Contract as a Mental Model by Rousseau (1995) theory adopting quantitative method approach with a cross-sectional research design. The reliability of the research instruments was determined using Cronbach's Alpha and a coefficient of $r > .6$ was reported in all the sub scales in the questionnaires. The data collected was analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) windows version 22 computer programme. Statistical tests, Pearson Product-Moment of Correlation and Regression were used to investigate the relationship between the variables. The study established that the employees' organizational commitment in general accounted for 57.3% as signified by Adjusted coefficient of $R^2 = .573$, of the variation in organizational commitment among non-academic staffs. The study recommends that employees' organizational commitment have a significant effect on the employees work output and so the institutions should ensure enabling work environment to workers, support and give motivational offers to employees and fulfil labour related promises. The contractual agreements should therefore be built and maintained in a stable, well-adjusted motivational force between the university non-academic staffs to enhance organizational commitments.

Keywords: Organizational Commitment, None-Academic Staffs, Public Universities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In light of trends toward globalization, restructuring and downsizing of organizations, employees' organizational commitment are playing an increasingly important role in contemporary employment relationships (Robinson, 2016). A study done by Yalabik (2014) indicates a common practice by public University administrative staffs doing very little to none-academic staffs discouraging a number of them from committing themselves to their duties.

On the other hand, it is equally noted that organizational performances in institutions of higher learning currently are characterized by minimal employee work commitment despite the improved working environments and pay. The reactions and perceptions the employees have towards the contractual promises made by the management constitute the laxity in work commitment due to none fulfillment of those contractual agreements. It is therefore important to understand the level of employees' organizational commitment among the none-academic staffs of higher learning institutions.

Based on the literatures reviewed, many institutional workforces have faced challenges in respect to management employees organizational work commitments of none-academic employees. Negative consequences to employees in turn have increased incidences of employees' absenteeism and high employee turnover ratio which elevate expenses and lower productivity which are directly linked to low employee commitment as a result of decreased employee motivation.

Although several studies in the developed world have examined the relationship between the organizational work commitment and organizational performance of product based industries, scanty literatures is available on the employees' organizational commitment among the none-teaching staff of higher learning institutions. Many have tried to study employees work commitment in other angles and provided recommendations by trying to use methods that were successful in other areas around the world and have met with failure, simply because employee organizational work commitment in the 21st century is unique and greatly depends on the organizations policy.

Level of Employees' Organizational Commitment

A study by Anthony (2017) on the employees' commitment and its impact on organizational performance indicated that the employees' commitment (Affective, Normative, Continuous) are significantly related to organizational performance in Eravurpatru Divisional Secretariat. The research findings reveal that there exists positive relationship between the three commitments and Organizational Performance. It has also been proved from the results that there exists strong correlation between the three independent variables and Organizational Performance. These outcomes in turn are associated with guiding the top management to working towards increasing employees' commitment level and hire employees who are likely to become linked to the organization who shall have a great impact and take the organization towards promising competitive edge.

According to Martin, Staines and Pate (2018), employees' organizational commitment is reflected in at least three general topics: active association with the organization, the predictable costs of leaving the organization and the obligation to remain in the organization. These three approaches are called affective, continual and normative commitment. Common to these three approaches is the attitude that the commitment is a psychological state characterized by the relationship of employees to the organization and implies a decision to continue the work in it. These psychological states also have different implications for the behaviour related to the workplace. Affective commitment refers to the employee's emotional attachment to the organization, its identification with the organization and involvement in its operation, namely, the agreement of objectives of the organization and of the individual. This is good. Employees who are very affectively dedicated to organization remain in it because they want to (Meyer & Allen, 2015),

According to Strojjanovic, Djokic and Djokic (2013) the causes of affective commitment narrow down to four categories: (1) personal characteristics, (2) structural characteristics (organizational), (3) the characteristics related to the type of work being performed, and (4) work experience. Although several researches were conducted for the purpose of integration of demographic characteristics (age, social status, gender and education level) to connect to the commitment, the resulting degree of correlation is not consistent. There are too many variables; such as job status, remuneration and working values that further affect the degree of this dependency. Few studies deal with the relationship between organizational characteristics and commitment. However, the findings by Strojjanovic, Djokic and Djokic indicate the connection between affective commitment and the decentralization of decision-making and formalization of policies and procedures of the organization. In addition, a significant number of studies were conducted dealing with the relationship between the variables of work experience of employees and their affective commitment. According to Meyer and Allen (2015), variables of work experience that supports affective commitment include equality in the distribution of rewards, clarity of roles and freedom from conflict at work place, the opportunity for advancement and inclusivity in decision-making.

Kickul and Lester (2001) outlined that continual commitment refers to the awareness of the costs associated with leaving the organization. The potential costs of leaving the organization involve the threat of wasting time and effort spent on the acquisition of non-communicable skills, loss of attractive benefits, waiver of privilege that brings long years of service, and the collapse of family and personal partnerships. In addition to costs related to leaving the organization, continual commitment will also develop in the absence of alternative employment opportunities. Kickul and Lester (2001) add that employees staying in the organization because of the continual commitment remain in them because they have to. Employees with high levels of normative commitment feel that they are obliged to remain in the organization.

Nguyen and Nguyen (2014) points out that the sense of obligation to remain in the organization can be realized from the internalization of normative pressures on the individual primarily to approach the organization itself (family or cultural reasons) or from the organizational orientation when influential individuals in the employee environment can exercise strong pressure on the employee to feel a moral responsibility towards the organization. However, normative commitment can also develop when the organization allows employees to be awarded in advance (for example, that is paid tuition fees for faculty) or compensates significant costs for the provision of employment (e.g. compensation for "hunting employees" or the costs associated with training for the job). Identifying these investments causes employees to feel obliged to commit to the organization until payment of the debt.

According to Guerrero (2008), the meaning of commitment of employees can best be explained using the theory of social exchange. The theory of social exchange according to Guerrero is based on an economic model of human behaviour, where the interaction processes between individuals are motivated by the desire to increase the rewards and reduce losses. The basic premise of the theory of social exchange is that the relationships that provide more reward than costs contribute to permanent mutual trust and attachment. Furthermore, these social transactions include both material benefits and psychological rewards, including status, loyalty and approval. For example, the workplace supervisor enables the employee's cash rewards, while in return the employee contributes by the personal commitment and expertise. Most often studied behaviour that is correlated with the commitment is money turnover in an organization. However, that focus on the turnover can be short-sighted (Oshagbemi, 2013).

According to Kinghts and Kennedy (2017), organizational performance depends more than just on simple maintenance of a stable workforce; employees have to perform assigned duties by relying on each other and must be willing to engage in activities that go beyond the role requires. Therefore, it seems reasonable to presume that the willingness of employees to contribute to the organizational performance will be influenced by the nature of the commitment they feel. Holt, Marques and Way (2012) noted that employees who wish to belong to the organization (affective commitment), as opposed to those who feel they need to belong (continuous commitment), or those who feel obliged to belong (normative commitment) are willing to make efforts for the benefit of their organization. Interestingly, of the studies registering correlations between commitment and performance, most of them used measures of affective commitment. It is possible that the obligation to remain in the organization carries with itself the obligation to contribute to it and, in that case the normative commitment is positively correlated with the efforts and performance (Guzzo & Noonan, 2014).

Continual commitment is perhaps the least likely option for a positive correlation with the performance. According to Hackman and Lawler (2011), employees whose term of office in the organization is based primarily on the needs may have little reason to do more than is necessary in order to maintain their existence in the organization. Brikend (2011) also found that organizations need employees who are willing to perform tasks that go beyond their standard duties and expectations of them, and to engage in additional activities at work. For this reason, the research will continue to examine the connection between these three components of commitment and multidimensional measurability of behaviour at work. Conway and Briner (2015) discovered that the measurability of conduct at work is positively correlated with measures of affective and normative commitment, but not with the continual commitment.

Research conducted by Steples (2019) reveals that affective commitment contributes significantly to the prediction of items related to the quality, readiness to sacrifice, and a willingness to share the knowledge. Normative commitment contributes only to the assumption about the readiness to sacrifice while a continuous commitment does not provide any significant predictions regarding organizational behaviour. The new findings therefore support the proposal that the three components of commitment have different implications for the behaviour at work other than turnover. The term closely linked to the commitment is the organizational "citizenship". It can be conceived as a global concept that includes all the positive, organizationally relevant behaviour of individual members of the organization. Therefore it includes traditional jobs that have defined roles, functional behaviour with additional roles and political behaviors such as full and responsible participation in the organization, which were usually omitted in previous studies of "citizenship" (Armstrong, 2011).

A widely accepted assumption is that better workplace environment motivates employees and produces better results (Freese & Schalk, 2018). Office environment can be described in terms of physical and behavioral components. These components can further be divided in the form of different independent variables (Guerrero, 2008). An organization's physical environment and its design and layout can affect employee behaviour in the workplace. Researchers estimate that

improvements in the physical design of the workplace may result in a 5-10 percent increase in employee productivity (Conway & Briner, 2015). Organizational commitment subscales (affective, normative, and continuance) have a significant impact on work performance dimensions, contextual and task performance (Holman and Axtell, 2016).

A substantial research has been conducted over the past decades to determine how employees' commitment to an organization develops (Mark & McDonald, 2011), as it is an important concept in terms of employee loyalty and efficiency for an organization (Bin, 2011). Organizational commitment stresses attachment to the organization, including its goals and values. Organizational commitment appears to develop slowly but consistently over time as individuals think about the relationship between themselves and their employer. Indeed, organizational commitment should be somewhat more stable over time (Anthony, 2017).

Certainly, employees' organizational commitment is one of the attitudes that could lead to high performance. Employees who are committed to their organization are more likely to be better performers than the less committed employees as they exert more effort on behalf of the organization towards its success and strive to achieve its goals and missions (Fauziah & Noordin, 2011). Employees with higher scores of commitment are expected to be more motivated and performing at highest levels of performance (Kruse, 2012). Researchers and scholars have defined organizational commitment differently. For example, Hausknecht (2012) described organizational commitment as the psychological likings and devotion that employees have to their organization.

Researchers argue that organizational commitment could be considered a bond or link between an employee and organization, as both employees and organizations benefit from employees' organizational commitment (Hodges, 2010; Hossein, Mohammad, Bitar, Fariba & Hosseinali, 2012). Moreover, John and Elyse (2010) define organizational commitment as "the feeling of responsibility that an employee has towards the mission of the organization." Alexandre (2012) studied organizational commitment mechanisms in utopian communities. Alexandre defines organizational commitment as "the willingness of social actors to give their energy and loyalty to social systems, the attachment of personality systems to social relations that are seen as self-expressive." In his study, Alexandre proposed a typology of commitment that includes three types of commitment namely: Continuance, cohesion and control. According to Alexandre theoretical framework the three types of commitment bind the individual's personality system to areas of the social system of an organization (relationships, roles and norms) and can thus represent an individual's readiness to follow the specified behaviour.

To ensure the achievement of firm goals, the organization creates an atmosphere of commitment and cooperation for its employees through policies that facilitate employee satisfaction. Satisfaction of human resource finds close links to highly motivated employees. Motivated employees then develop loyalty or commitment to the firm resulting to greater productivity and lower turnover rates (Kabir and Parvin, 2011). The workforces today are filled with various mindsets. Over the past few years, there have been numerous supports on human capital development, lifelong learning and continuous attention on soft skill development. Nevertheless, many a times, issues are only attended to at the surface level but not to the roots of the cause. Human beings are highly associated with emotion and intelligence. Therefore, the requirement to fulfill human need hierarchy is rather an important aspect especially on satisfaction and motivation (Yukthamarani et al., 2013).

Employee commitment always plays a very key role in improving the organizational performance. The organizational performance can be measured through a lot of ways for example, company employee turnover, return on equity etc. Employee commitment can be enhanced through their involvement in assessment construction and providing them with the chance for better insight on the whole procedure of the organization performance measurement (Dost and Ahmed, 2011). Igella (2014) recommended that the research should be carried out in another sector in order to broaden the understanding of the term commitment in relation to that sector. The reason for carrying out further research in that direction is that the factors that may strongly influence employee commitment in the service industry could differ in the production industry.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Rousseau's Psychological Contract Model (Nonway & Briner, 2005)

Rousseau (2015) is widely acknowledged as having had the greatest influence on psychological contract research since the writings of Levinson and Schein (2004). Rousseau marked a fundamental shift in understanding the meaning and function of psychological contract and how it could be empirically investigated. She placed greater emphasis on the promissory

nature of psychological contracts defining them as an individuals’ beliefs regarding the terms and conditions of reciprocal exchange agreement between that focal person and another party. She argued that once a promise has been made and a consideration offered in exchange for it, this would be binding to the parties and some set of reciprocal obligations must be observed. In noting the obligatory quality of psychological contract expectation, Rousseau emphasizes promises rather than expectations although there is still much debate around the definition and managing of promises and the extent to which they can be separated from the notion of obligations and expectations.

The second important change argued by Rousseau was moving away from viewing the psychological contract as one involving the perspectives of two interconnected parties towards seeing it as an individual level subjective phenomenon “existing in the eye of beholders. Rousseau focuses much on the individual employee’s perceptions as the most important influence on feelings, attitudes and behaviour. Rousseau suggested that it was not possible for organizations to have psychological contracts as they can only be held by the people and not abstract entities. Organizations cannot perceive though their individual managers can themselves personally perceive a psychological contract with employees and respond accordingly (Rousseau, 2015).

The earlier thinkers identified basic human needs as the driving force being the formation of expectations. Rousseau on the other hand suggested that the psychological contracts are formed by the individual’s perceptions of their own and the organizations behaviour in terms of explicit verbal or written promises or implicit promises arising from consistent and repeated patterns of behaviour by parties to the contract. Other than being formed by some deeper-level motives, such as needs, Rousseau believes that it is primarily an individual perception of observable behaviour that constitute psychological contract.

Earlier explanations of the psychological contract and how they affects behaviour tended to focus on the extent to which employee perceived a reasonable match between the inducements offered by the organization and their own contributions irrespective of what had been promised. In contrast, Rousseau proposes the idea of “violation” as the main mechanism linking the psychological contract to various outcomes. Violation is defined as failure of organizations or other parties to respond to an employee’s contribution in ways the individual believes they are obliged to do so (Rousseau, 2016).

Profound influence of Rousseau’s ideas in generating future research and interest in the psychological contract can be accounted for in a number of ways. The most well documented explanations mentioned earlier is that the psychological contract was seen as way of understanding contemporary changes to the employment relationship during the 1990’s. The second explanation for its influence is Rousseau’s careful demarcations of the psychological contract both from previous conceptualizations and from related ideas such as equity and met expectations, thus allowing researchers to start investigating what appeared to be a new and exciting idea.

Third compared to previous conceptualizations emphasize unconscious need driven expectations. Rousseau approach to psychological contract as observable promises made it quantifiable and readily researchable through straight forward and traditional research methods such as questionnaire surveys. Lastly, the idea of violation provided researchers with a relatively simple mechanism which could be used to help understand and research relationships between the psychological contract and outcome.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

Ninety five none-academic staffs were sampled for the study. For a population of one hundred and eight (108) staffs, ninety five (95) were adequate according to Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The Sample Size was therefore summarized in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Sample Size

Category of Respondents	Total	Sample Number	Percentage (%)
None-Academic Staffs	108	95	87.9%

Data Collection

This study used questionnaires as the major instrument for data collection. The questionnaires for this study contained pre-developed closed ended items and a rating scale with pre-determined responses. The none-academic staffs responded to the same questionnaires irrespective of their levels.

Reliability Analysis

The measure of internal consistency of the items in each subscale was explored to investigate internal reliability of the instruments. Creswell (2014) asserts that internal consistence is the degree to which an instrument is reliable; error free and consistent across time and across the various items in the scale. Although there are several methods of investigating level of internal consistency, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient is the most reliable test of inter-item consistency reliability. Hence, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient analysis was used to measure the internal consistency of the instruments, because it is the most consistent test of inter-item consistency reliability for Likert scaled or rating scaled questionnaire. The reliability for multi-item opinion items were computed separately for all the subscales in the none-academic staff questionnaires and the coefficient alpha of these variables were reported in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Internal Consistency: Cronbach’s Alpha Results for the Questionnaire

Scale	No. Items	Item Deleted	Cronbach’s alpha	Conclusion
Organization commitment	16	None	.806	Reliable

Table 1.2 reveals that all the four sub-scales met the required level of internal consistency with the Cronbach’s alpha values ranging from a low of 0.691 (Employee Recognition Questionnaire) to a high of 0.806 (Organization Commitment Questionnaire). These findings were in line with the recommendation by Oso and Onen (2013) that a coefficient of 0.60 is of moderate reliability while coefficient of 0.70 and above indicates that the instrument has a high reliability. The Cronbach’s alpha for all the subscales reveals that the instruments had sufficient reliability for the study. However, some two items (7 and 13) had to be deleted first from the sub-scale of employee recognition questionnaires. This resulted to an increase in Cronbach’s alpha, that is, it caused improvement in the internal consistency in this questionnaire. However, it was noted that all items were now correlated with the total scale to a good degree in all the subscales, after deleting the items which did not appropriately hang out well with others. Therefore, the questionnaires were suitable for data collection because they adequately measured the constructs for which they were intended to measure.

Method of Data Analysis

The descriptive statistics have been used to generate mean and variance.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Employees Organizational Commitment among None-Academic Staffs of Public Universities

The study sought to investigate the level of organizational commitment among the none-academic staffs of Public Universities along the lake region in Kenya. Organizational commitment was implied by their level of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction was measured using sixteen Likert-scaled items whose contracts were indicators’ of organizational commitment. Using the five level responses, from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5), by the respondents of job satisfaction, responses between 1 and 2 were considered weak which is negative to the organizational commitments while responses above 3 were considered strong and positive for the organizational commitment. The views were summarized in the means and their standard deviations, as shown in Table 1.3.

The results of the survey revealed that there is generally moderate level of organizational commitment among the none-academic staffs at the public Universities. This was reflected by overall scale of 3.14 (SD=0.26) in the organizational commitment scale of 1 to 5, with all the items ranging from a low of 2.00 to a high of 3.48. This implies that, in general, the none-academic staffs are somewhat satisfied with their job, hence they readily identify with the university and its goals. For example, on affective commitment, the results of the survey established that on the average (mean =3.12; SD=0.74) employees would wish to continue working for the university. Similarly, the results shows that employees (Scale =3.14; SD=1.05) always feel valued as part of the organizational system. By the same token, the results of the survey indicated

that the staffs holds the feeling that they fit well in the organization and are somehow satisfied with their work, as reflected by a mean response rate of 3.04. On whether they have a say on what they do, it emerged that the staffs agreed that their voices are always heard in their work place (Mean= 3.21).

In regard to affective commitment, the study findings established that, averagely the none-academic staffs wants to continue staying in the university and that they believe there is an opportunity of achieving something worthwhile within the organization. This implied being affectively committed to the university, to some extent, as interpreted by their level of job satisfaction. Similarly, it emerged that at (mean=3.35; SD=1.14) the respondents were in agreement that they are able to change the things they don't like about their job, they alluded that there is some (mean=3.48; SD=1.08) amount of change and variety in their job agreeing (mean=3.35; SD=1.06) that they have a chance to use their abilities within their job, reflecting some level of job satisfaction among the staffs. On the same note, the findings of the survey show that (mean=3.31; SD=1.10), the staffs are able to do their job without a supervisor worrying them. In fact, the respondents accepted (mean=3.42; SD=1.05) that they have enough time to do their job properly and they observed that there are chances of achieving something worthwhile within their work place. This implies that the staffs at the Public Universities are moderately contented with their jobs, indicative of moderate level of affective commitment.

Table 1.3: Level of Organizational Commitment (n=89)

Indicators of Organizational Commitment		Mean	Standard deviation
1.	I would wish to continue working in this university	3.12	0.74
2.	I feel that I fit well in this organization and am satisfied with my work	3.04	1.00
3.	I have a say about the way I do things in my job	3.21	1.19
4.	I feel valued in as an employee in this university	3.14	1.05
5.	I am able to change the things I don't like about my job	3.35	1.14
6.	There is a chance to use my abilities within my job	3.35	1.06
7.	There is amount of change and variety in my job	3.48	1.08
8.	I am able to do my job without a supervisor worrying me	3.31	1.10
9.	I have enough time to do my job properly	3.42	1.05
10.	There are chances of achieving something worthwhile	3.45	0.94
11.	Physical conditions at work (cleanliness, noise level) are conducive	3.11	1.20
12.	The amount of pressure or stress is minimal	2.77	1.26
13.	I have the opportunity to do challenging and interesting work	3.46	1.11
14.	I am satisfied with the amount of pay I get	2.00	1.16
15.	I have access to promotion opportunities	2.78	1.08
16.	I have opportunities to grow as a person and be myself	3.27	1.29
Mean average level of organizational commitment		3.14	0.26

On the flip flop, with respect to normative commitment, the study results reveal that employees in the universities felt they should continue staying and working at the universities (mean=3.12; SD=0.74). This was because they feel that leaving their current job in the university would have disastrous consequences and they feel a sense of guilt about the possibility of leaving. It emerged that reasons for such guilt vary, but are often concerned with the staffs' feeling that in leaving the organization they would create a void in knowledge or skills.

Similarly, on continuance commitment, it became clear that the staff members feel the need to stay at their university. This may be because of their lack of work alternatives in terms of condition of work and remuneration elsewhere. For instance, the staffs are fairly satisfied (mean=3.11; SD=1.20) with physical conditions at work (cleanliness, noise level) which they are of the feeling are conducive. Likewise, the respondents have the opportunity to do challenging and interesting work, as reflected from a mean response rate of 3.46, with a standard deviation of 1.11. In fact, none-academic staffs of the institutions are fairly satisfied with their job, because they are moderately convinced at a mean of 3.27 and a standard deviation of 1.29 that they have opportunities to grow as a person and to be themselves.

On the contrary, the results of the survey established that although the respondents alluded to be enjoying some level of job satisfaction, they are not satisfied with the amount of pay they get as compensation to their services, they argued not being satisfied with the amount of pay they get, as reflected by a response rate at a low mean of 2.00 and (SD=1.16). Equally, the results of the survey indicates that the amount of pressure or stress at work is fairly large (mean=2.77, SD=1.26). On the same note, the study findings established that the staffs hold a general feeling that they do not have access to promotional opportunities in the university. This implies that the none-academic staffs are loosely emotionally attached to the university because a number of them claimed to have stagnated in specific grades for quite a long time. The results of the study imply that although the staffs are committed and believe in the institutional values, they are reluctantly willing to put out effort to meet the university goals.

From the descriptive statistics the respondents were grouped by their level of organizational commitment. The variable was collapsed into three ordinal categories; Low (1.00-2.33), Moderate (2.34-3.66) and High (3.67-5.00). The findings are presented in figure 4.2 and discussed.

Figure 1.1: Level of Organizational Commitment (n=89)

The figure shows that more than a half (53.0%) of administrative staffs in Rongo University are moderately committed to their university, 13.3% are low in their commitment level and 33.7% are of high commitment. The findings show that the respondents were in agreement with the question that employees’ organizational demands for perfection if met will always lead to organizational commitment. This well stated by Brammers (2007) who further argued that employees who feel that their organization values their input are likely to be a lot more committed to the organization because they do not want to lose that trust from the organization. The employees, who strongly lack the ability to cope with their new tasks, are more likely to have a negative response to such demands from their organization. Consequently, they are likely to express lower levels of commitment to their organizations. The findings indicate that the respondents strongly agreed that their organization has a strong work ethic. This agrees with Carrol (2008) statement that, the work ethics of an organization can be identified as a factor that has a very serious influence on organizational commitment.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The research question focused on finding out the employees’ organizational commitment among the none-academic Staffs of public Universities along the Lake region in Kenya. From the findings, it was discovered that employees’ organizational commitments have a very strong influence on the levels of employees’ performance at work place. The influential factors to employees work commitment included; organizational dependability, effectiveness of the organizations social processes and the organizational climate. The discussion indicated that the above three factors had a greater influence thus making them strong organizational factors that influence employee commitment within a working environment.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher recommends a reasonable match between the inducements offered by the institutions and the employees own contributions irrespective of what had been promised. Most institutions need employees who are willing to perform tasks that go beyond their standard duties and in achieving this, the employer must provide enabling work environment, motivational remunerations, besides adherence to work ethics and labour laws.

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